

CONCEPTION
SAFETY EVIDENCE ECOSYSTEM

WORK PACKAGE 1

DRAFT

Document Title

Prescription medicines in pregnancy
and Known Risks: An Overview

Due Date: month 30

Version: 1.1 date: 28.6.22

Version 1.2 date 11.8.23

Task No: 1.2.5

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Task 1.2.5 aims to define a standard core set of clinically relevant maternal, perinatal and childhood outcomes that should be consistently evaluated to adequately address regulatory requirements to inform HCPs and patients on medication use during pregnancy (e.g. via medication labels, SmPCs)

Prescription medicines in pregnancy and Known Risks: An Overview

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Purpose of this document

Adverse perinatal outcomes remain an important public health issue. Identification of inter-generational developmental adverse drug reactions (ADRs) poses complex questions, including those surrounding medicines exposures and co-exposures. The inter-generational and transgenerational developmental ADRs under consideration are those affecting subsequent generations, broadly congruent with ICH (2020) categories “implantation to closure of hard palate, closure of hard palate to end of pregnancy, and birth to weaning and sexual maturity” (C-F). This document lists exposures that warrant consideration in pharmaco-epidemiological and pharmacovigilance studies relating to pregnant women.

These lists indicate which co-exposures should be accounted, depending on outcome of interest. We advise:

- ***Identification***
- ***Exclusion***
- ***Separate reporting of excluded subjects***
- ***Listing unidentifiable aetiologies in the study limitations***

Sensitivity analyses may be useful, where numbers are sufficient.

Lists have been compiled from secondary sources, and encompass regulatory documents (see bibliography). The length of the lists is due to the level of details in these sources: the problem for investigators is that omission of any aspect of multifactorial aetiologies may lead to inaccurate conclusions.

This document is not confined to known teratogens, reviewed elsewhere (Gomes et al 2021). Rather, it addresses the pregnancy and developmental outcomes important to women and their families.

How to accommodate known risks?

We suggest that appropriate lists are selected and included in protocols, either for action or as limitations.

For each outcome investigated:

- Identify all aetiologies listed
- Report each exposure, even if numbers can only be disclosed as <5 (or there are 0 exposures)
- Where the exposures cannot be ascertained, note each of these in the study limitations.
- Report each exposure against outcome(s) of interest as *a priori* subgroups, numbers & governance permitting (This is important where the numbers of women affected is not negligible e.g. diabetes, substance misuse (Jordan et al 2019.) Where this is impossible, note in the text and, if appropriate, the study limitations.
- Exclude all exposed (at risk) pregnancies from the relevant analyses (if this is done once for all co-exposures together, it will minimize the work involved)
- Consider confining this to the highest risk aetiologies (even if rare).
- Consider a sensitivity analysis with these included.
- Alternatively, this can be reversed, so that the first analysis is ‘all participants’ and the sensitivity analysis is ‘without the pregnancies exposed

or co-exposed to known or suspected teratogens or cause of adverse outcomes’.

- If the medicines or conditions of interest are listed, the known risk can be mentioned in the introduction. (It makes no sense to exclude them.)

Alternative approach

If exposures cannot be identified earlier, cases exposed to the medicine of interest should be checked for the less frequent and less likely aetiologies, after the large groups (e.g. diabetes, substance misuse) have been excluded and reported (e.g. Jordan et al 2016, 2019). Where rare outcomes are considered (e.g. severe congenital heart disease) even two or three cases with co-exposures can affect the reported risk. When requested, EUROmediCAT produces for review case lists showing medication exposures, maternal illnesses, and family history as recorded by the registries from available notes.

Rationale for this document

When examining inter- and transgenerational adverse drug reactions, the agent under investigation, and prescribed medicines in general, may not be the only exposure or possible aetiology of adverse perinatal outcomes. Accounting for these is discussed elsewhere (Damase et al, task 1.2, Jordan et al 2022).

Comedications are of interest in medication safety studies in pregnancy because of their potential to act as confounders, or moderators, or to interact with the medication(s) of interest in the study. The numbers of infants exposed and affected can be very small, but some outcomes are also rare, ***and very low numbers of co-exposed cases can affect the study’s interpretation.*** For example, the association between anti-depressant prescriptions and substance misuse may complicate the interpretation of the associations with adverse outcomes (Jordan et al 2016, 2019).

Confounders [see glossary, Jordan et al 2022] are associated with both the medication exposure of interest, and the outcome (congenital anomaly, neurodevelopment, preterm birth, SGA), so a preselection of potential priority confounders involves identifying known teratogens. Any association with the medication exposure of interest depends on that medication and its indication. While the traditional way of dealing with confounders is to stratify by them in the statistical analysis, this is usually not possible due to the very small numbers of co-exposed cases. At the same time, one or two co-exposures can have a considerable impact on odds ratios based on few overall exposures. Therefore, an alternative strategy is to exclude any exposures in the pregnancy population to rare, known teratogens (a very small proportion of all pregnancies), and to check for the presence in the study population of potentially influential cases of co-exposure to less well-established teratogens or medicines related to other adverse outcomes. Interaction with the medication exposure of interest depends on the mechanism of action, and needs to be assessed on a study specific basis. The lists below, while not exhaustive, may offer a pragmatic approach.

Lists of ATC and ICD10 codes are appended. Medicines associated with high risk of teratogenicity, regardless of frequency of use are listed in Table 1.

List 1. Medicines with the Highest risks for major anomalies (all or any)

Other adverse perinatal outcomes are listed below

We suggest: exclude and report as *a priori* subgroups.

Medicines (see Table 1 for ATC codes)

- Coumarins
- Valproic acid derivatives* (including children of those exposed *in utero* (Martin et al 2022))
- Other AEDs (Veronili et al 2017) Risks increase with combinations.
 - Clobazam
 - Ethosuximide
 - Vigabatrin
 - Topiramate
 - Phenytoin – fosphenytoin likely similar risk (no oral formulation) (BNF 2023)
 - Phenobarbital
 - Primidone (a barbiturate)
- Antineoplastic agents (L01) are considered as a group in List 2 (less frequently used), and some are subject to pregnancy prevention programmes. Many medicines in L01 are either known teratogens or lack data relating to human pregnancy. Accordingly, with large data sets, it may be prudent to exclude women exposed to any antineoplastic agents.

Other substances with high risks

- Radiopharmaceuticals V09 (The list of ATC codes under V09 is long, and most agents will not appear in primary care data)
- Heavy alcohol use (often noted in primary care as a referral to services)
- Substance misuse (as referral to services, as deemed necessary by primary care teams)

Conditions

- Type 1 diabetes – often identified as insulin prescriptions

All Medicines with a pregnancy prevention program are high risk

These medicines are known to confer a high risk of anomalies, sometimes based on ICH (2020) criteria for data extrapolation from animal studies. In European women of childbearing age, exposure occurs only rarely, if at all. However, the database should be checked, and those exposed excluded from the analysis. Numbers affected should be reported, even if as 0 or <5. An alternative approach is to check exposed cases to ensure no co-exposure to these high-risk medicines.

- Thalidomide & analogues
 - Thalidomide L04AX02
 - Lenalidomide L04AX04
 - Pomalidomide L04AX06
- Retinoids (oral)
 - Isotretinoin* D10AD04, D10BA01, D10AD54
 - Acitretin D05BB02
 - Alitretinoin D11AH04, L01XX2
 - Tretinoin L01XX14

- Pulmonary hypertension treatments (no PPP, but instructed 'avoid', BNF 2023)
 - Ambrisentan C02KX02
 - Bosentan* C02KX01
 - Macitentan C02KX04
 - Riociguat* C02KX05
- Vismodegib L01XX43 (for skin cancers, no PPP in BNF)
- Immunosuppressants
 - Eculizumab L04AA25 (no PPP in BNF)
 - fingolimod L04AA27 (for MS) (no PPP in BNF)
 - mycophenolate mofetil / mycophenolic acid L04AA06
 - tacrolimus (ICH 2020) L04AD02 (preterm birth, SGA)
 - Azathioprine. (preterm birth, SGA, spontaneous abortion [BNF 2023]) (L04AX01)
 - Methotrexate (Verberne et al 2019) (L01BA01, L04AX03)
- cytotoxics
 - hydroxycarbamide L01XX05 (no PPP in BNF)
 - bexarotene L01XX25
- immune modulators
 - leflunomide L04AA13 (no PPP in BNF)
- bisphosphonate
 - zoledronic acid M05BA08, M05BB08 (no PPP in BNF)
- eptotermin alfa M05BC02 (not in BNF)

There are known risks to healthcare professionals handling cytotoxic agents during pregnancy (BNF 2023). Such exposure is not always captured in congenital anomalies registers, but should be accounted where possible.

List 2 Risk is supported by considerable evidence, but less frequently used.

These medicines are known to confer additional risk, but less so than the medicines listed above.

Options are 'exclude and report' or check exposed cases.

Medicines (see Table 1 for ATC codes)

- Antineoplastics: most are teratogenic, contraception is mandated, and administration during the 1st trimester is not advised (BNF 2023, van Gerwen et al 2021). This indicates that all L01 ATCs (antineoplastic agents) should be considered.
 - Alkylating agents (L01A) (e.g. cisplatin, cyclophosphamide, doxorubicin)
 - Carbimazole (H03BB) (methimazole outside UK)
 - Antimetabolites (L01B)
 - Methotrexate* (L01BA01) (BNF 2023) (Aminopterin no longer marketed)
 - Penicillamine M01CC
 - Ribavirin* J05AP01
 - Griseofulvin* D01AA08, D01BA01
 - Fluconazole regular use @400-800mg/ day
 - Exenatide (for type 2 diabetes)

- Progesterones
- Diethylstilbestrol
- Finasteride (for prostatic hyperplasia or alopecia in men, unlicensed for hirsutism in women)
- Iodine, including topical
- Immunomodulators / immunotherapy: L04 (immunosuppressants) uncertainty remains regarding recently marketed medicines (Borgers et al 2021)

List 3 Conditions conferring risks

Some conditions, medicated or unmedicated, increase the risk of adverse infant outcomes. For many conditions, there are increased risks of preterm birth, small for gestational age and congenital anomalies. The risks are probably lower than those associated with type 1 diabetes (above). See Table 3, below.

- PKU (phenylketonuria)
- SLE (systemic lupus erythematosus)
- Congenital anomaly in mother
- Congenital anomaly in maternal sibling
- CMV exposure
- Rubella exposure
- Chickenpox exposure
- Toxoplasmosis exposure

Febrile illness (Graham 2020, Czeizel et al 2008). It may not be possible to identify all episodes of febrile illness from primary care databases, due to under-reporting by patients and professionals, and the complexity of the coding needed. This should be mentioned in the limitations section of the study.

Cancer and cancer treatments. Cancer diagnosis can be ascertained from hospital admission data or cancer databases. Coding is likely to be complex, due to the many types of cancer and their classifications. It may be easier to identify whether an individual has a record in a cancer database, if a comprehensive database exists. Hospital admissions data will not identify some skin cancers, which are not usually associated with chemotherapy.

List 4. Exposures conferring some risk

There is less evidence of additional risk of congenital anomalies associated with these exposures. However, checks should be undertaken, either in sensitivity analyses or by examination of exposed cases.

Medicines

- Carbamazepine (Veroniki et al 2017)
- Aminoglycosides (ototoxicity, nephrotoxicity, not structural birth defects)

Other substances and exposures

Without geospatial analysis, it may be impossible to account for some of these exposures. This can be noted in the study limitations.

- Lindane P03AB02
- Pesticides (likely not recorded. P03 gives insect repellants, and treatments)

- Pollution, landfill, environmental exposures.

List 5. Uncertain additional risk

For some exposures, additional risk of any or all adverse developmental outcomes is not universally accepted.

Sensitivity analyses and checks of exposed cases are advisable (See table 2 for ATC codes)

- SSRIs / SNRIs / other antidepressants (Jordan et al 2016, 2019)
- Fluconazole single use – not regular use @400-800mg/ day
- gold salts, aurothiomalate (uncertain, no information in UKTIS)
- lithium (NO5AN);
- corticosteroids: oral – clefts, inhaled – possible association with congenital cataracts (Garne et al 2016)
- ergot derivatives (ergotamine)
- statins – advised to avoid (BNF 2023)
- Methylene blue V03AB17, V04CG05 This is iv only for cyanide poisoning. BNF says ‘no information’. This is used rarely, and will only be identified from hospital records, as a *stat* dose. (old FDA category X*)
- Tetracyclines (evidence in animal studies) teeth & bone staining, hepatotoxicity in humans
- Levonorgestrel G03AC03, G03AD01, G03FA11, G03FB09, G03AA07, G03AB03 (a contraceptive) old FDA category X*, BNF (2023) indicates ‘not known to be harmful’ with oral use
- Ulipristal G03AD02, G03XB02 (a contraceptive) FDA category X*, BNF (2023) says ‘avoid’ regular use (for fibroids)
- Colchicine
- Misoprostol (an abortifacient)
- Mifepristone (an abortifacient)
- Ondansetron (risk of facial clefts)
- Rifaximin (based on animal data) prescribed for diarrhoea
- Sulfasalazine (BNF 2023 advises co-administration of folate)
- Other folate antagonists (risks suspected but unproven): trimethoprim, triamterene, cimetidine
- Antipsychotics (Creeley & Denton 2019)
 - Pregabalin – N03AX16 (Bastow 2017)
 - Oxcarbazepine (currently too few data) - N03AF02
 - Aspirin (high dose) UKTIS. High doses have possible teratogenic effects. In third trimester, risk of foetal or maternal bleeding (BNF 2023) N02BA01

Like all lists in this document, amendments will be needed as further studies are completed.

* Footnote: FDA category X. Pre-2015, the US Food and Drugs Administration (FDA), some medicines were classified as: Studies in animals or humans have demonstrated fetal abnormalities and/or there is positive evidence of human fetal risk based on adverse reaction data from investigational or marketing experience, and the risks involved in use of the drug in pregnant women clearly outweigh potential benefits. (see Tablet 4) <https://www.drugs.com/pregnancy-categories.html#>

Recently marketed medicines will not have a FDA classification. However, inclusion in the X category indicates an enduring perception of risk.

Risk uncertain – likely no additional risk

Lamotrigine (Veroniki et al 2017) N03AX09

Gabapentin (Veroniki et al 2017) N03AX12

Macrolides: erythromycin, claritromycin, azithromycin - uncertain risk (MHRA 2021).

List 6. Exposures associated with preterm birth, small for gestation age (SGA) and congenital anomalies

- Insulin, AEDs & coumarins in first trimester are associated with preterm birth.
- AEDs are associated with SGA < 10th centile
- Coumarins are associated with SGA < 3rd centile (Jordan et al 2019).
- Some AEDs (zonisamide, phenobarbital, topiramate [BNF 2023]) are associated with these adverse outcomes.
- Aspirin, SGA in high doses (BNF 2023) N02BA01

List 7 Exposures that are probably not teratogenic, but are foetotoxic or affect other outcomes

The analysis of these outcomes should follow the suggestions above: identification, separate reporting, and sensitivity analyses. For rare exposures, checks of exposed cases may be sufficient.

Benzodiazepines are associated with preterm birth and SGA (Creeley & Denton 2019, Grigoriadis et al 2020). All benzodiazepines are probably associated with an increased incidence of facial clefts (Enato et al 2011). Triazolam (N05CD05) was FDA category X (it is no longer prescribable, but may occur in older records.)

- Z drugs – SGA & preterm birth
- Antipsychotics – SGA
- Ergot derivatives – SGA & preterm birth
- atenolol / beta blockers – intra-uterine growth restriction (IUGR) / SGA
- oral corticosteroids (preterm birth, SGA) (Davies et al 2020)
- beta2 agonists SGA (Davies et al 2020)
- antidepressants SGA (Jordan et al 2019)
- angiotensin converting enzyme inhibitors or angiotensin II blockers (C09): trimesters 2 & 3 (includes Aliskiren* C09XA02, C09XA53, C09XA52, C09XA54, C09DX02, FDA category X) (renal damage)
- aminoglycosides – ototoxic, nephrotoxic
- levothyroxine (N03AA) – impact depends on achieving the correct replacement dose. Under-replacement, even in subclinical disease, is associated with preterm birth and pregnancy loss (Rao et al 2019), and over-replacement with preterm birth (Lemieux et al 2021). Overt hypothyroidism, which is treatable, is associated with pregnancy loss, preterm birth, SGA and neurodevelopmental problems (Alexander et al 2017). Levothyroxine may be regarded as a marker, rather than a cause of adverse outcomes.
- Oxytocin G02AC01, H01BB02, H01BB02, H01BB02 - premature uterine contractions (FDA category X, above)
- Trimethadione – foetal loss

- Misoprostol – foetal loss
- Danazol (all androgens) – virilization
- Pregabalin – SGA N03AX16 (Bastow 2017)
- NSAIDs (premature closure of *ductus arteriosus*)

List 8. Neurodevelopmental outcomes

Valproate

Other AEDs: phenytoin, carbamazepine

Levothyroxine under-replacement

Conflicting evidence for: SSRIs/ SNRIs, oxytocin, benzodiazepines

List 9. Miscarriage

- Auto-immune conditions, including thyroid disorders
- Febrile illness (Giakoumelou et al 2016), sexually transmitted disease is an additional risk
- Intra-uterine infection, possible association with urinary tract infections (UTI)
- Alcohol
- Smoking
- Substance misuse
- Obesity
- Chromosomal anomalies
- Diabetes
- Severe hypertension
- Severe renal disease
- NSAIDs
- Misoprostol
- Oxytocin
- Stimulant laxatives (Dathe and Schaefer 2019)
- Methotrexate
- Retinoids
- Radiation exposure
- Lead, mercury, arsenic, solvents, pesticides (identification of exposure is likely to be a limitation)
- Anatomical anomalies (uterus or cervix)
- Polycystic ovaries
- Severe malnutrition
- Maternal age
(<https://www.webmd.com/baby/4-common-causes-miscarriage#1>)
- Macrolides: erythromycin, claritromycin, azithromycin - uncertain (MHRA 2021).

List 10. Breastfeeding

For many women, it is important to know whether a prescribed medicine will make breastfeeding more difficult. The complex physiology of lactation is vulnerable to disruption, particularly by medicines that:

- affect serotonergic pathways:
 - SSRIs, (Jordan et al 2019, Nyárady et al 2020)
- antagonise prolactin:

- amphetamines,
- oestrogens,
- ergotamine derivatives (bromocriptine, cabergoline, lisuride, pergolide, methylergometrine), including for routine management of third stage of labour (Jordan et al 2009),
- aripiprazole,
- promethazine,
- diuretics,
- injected corticosteroids
- reduce endogenous oxytocin release
 - alcohol,
 - opioids (including in labour [Jordan et al 2005]),
 - sympathomimetics,
 - anticholinergics) (Lawrence & Schaefer 2015, Anderson 2017a, 2017b).
 - exogenous oxytocin (Jordan et al 2009)

Where breastfeeding is considered, either as an outcome itself or in association with neurodevelopment, exposure to medicines affecting breastfeeding should be considered and accounted (Jordan et al 2022). Many of these preparations are administered during labour, in hospital. In primary care, exposure is sometimes inferred from the mode of delivery or administration of epidural analgesia, where recorded. The transfer of medicines to infants *via* breastmilk is described elsewhere (Verstegen et al 2020). Table 5 holds ATC codes for medicines not included elsewhere.

Exposures with considerable uncertainty

Some agents with weak or conflicting evidence of foetotoxicity or teratogenicity have been omitted from these lists: morphine, codeine (not reported in standard works and well used); azoles (usually topical applications); antimalarials (evidence uncertain); antivirals (systemic use associated with severe illness); methylphenidate (uncertain); endothelin receptor antagonists (new); enzyme replacement therapy (uncertain, animal studies reported); monoclonal antibodies (associated with severe illness) (Gomes et al 2021). Investigators may wish to consider these.

Summary and conclusion

This document lists medicines and other exposures that may present a risk to the foetus, and should, ideally, be accounted for when investigating possible harms. Strategies for handling these risks in epidemiological analyses are suggested. Separate analyses for pregnancies at increased risk will clarify the impact of the exposure of interest, and facilitate targeted recommendations. Multi-centre studies are strengthened if at least one databank can account for each exposure: for example, some have data on substance misuse, and others have data on in-hospital prescribing.

Appendices

ATC and ICD10 codes lists

Table 1 ATCs for highest risk medicines

Drug	Code
Coumarins	B01AA01, B01AA02 B01AA03 B01AA04 B01AA07 B01AA08
Valproic acid derivatives	N03AG01
Clobazam	N05BA09
Ethosuximide	N03AD01
Combinations	N03AD51
Vigabatrin	N03AG04
Topiramate	N03AX11
Phenytoin	N03AB02
Combinations	N03AB52
Phenobarbital	N03AA02
Radiopharmaceuticals	V09
• Thalidomide & analogues	
• Thalidomide	L04AX02
• Lenalidomide	L04AX04
• Pomalidomide	L04AX06
• Retinoids (oral)	
• Isotretinoin	D10AD04, D10BA01, D10AD54
• Acitretin	D05BB02
• Alitretinoin	D11AH04, L01XX2
• Tretinoin	L01XX14
Less frequently used	
• Pulmonary hypertension treatments (no PPP in BNF)	
• Ambrisentan	C02KX02
• Bosentan	C02KX01
• Macitentan	C02KX04
• Riociguat	C02KX05
• Vismodegib (for skin cancers)	L01XX43
• Immunosuppressants	
• Eculizumab (no PPP in BNF)	L04AA25
• fingolimod (for MS) (no PPP in BNF)	L04AA27
• mycophenolate mofetil / mycophenolic acid L04AA06	
▪ tacrolimus (ICH 2020) (also renal damage, preterm birth, SGA)	L04AD02
• Azathioprine. (also preterm birth, SGA, spontaneous abortion [BNF 2021])	L04AX01
• Methotrexate (Verberne et al 2019)	L01BA01, L04AX03

WP1 Table of exposures with known risks

• cytotoxics	
• hydroxycarbamide (no PPP in BNF)	L01XX05
• bexarotene	L01XX25
• immune modulators	
• leflunomide (no PPP in BNF)	L04AA13
• bisphosphonate	M05BA08, M05BB08
• zoledronic acid (no PPP in BNF)	
• eptotermin alfa (not in BNF)	M05BC02
Carbimazole (methimazole)	H03BB01
Methotrexate	L01BA01 L04AX03
Azathioprine	L04AX01
Fluconazole Topical	J02AC01 D01AC15
Exenatide	A10BJ01
Antineoplastics	L01****
Alkylating agents	L01A***
Cyclophosphamide	L01AA01
Antimetabolites	
Folic Acid analogues (shown below)	L01BA**
Purine analogues	L01BB02 L01BB03 L01BB04 L01BB05 L01BB06 L01BB07
Pyrimidine analogues	L01BC01 L01BC02 L01BC03 L01BC04 L01BC05 L01BC06 L01BC07 L01BC08 L01BC09 L01BC52 L01BC53 L01BC59
Progesterone	G03DA04
Hydroxyprogesterone	G03DA03
Medroxyprogesterone	G03DA02
Finasteride	D11AX10 G04CB01
Iodine	D08AG03 D03AX01 B03AA11

WP1 Table of exposures with known risks

	<p>V09AX03 V09IX03 V09XA03 V09GB02 V09XA01 V09AB01, V09AB02V09AB03 D08AG01, D08AG02 D09AA09 D11AC06 G01AX11 R02AA15 S01AX18 V10XA53</p>
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* indicates 'wild card' digits

Table 2 ATCs for Medicines with uncertain risks

Medication	Code
SSRIs	<p>N06AB02, N06AB03, N06AB04, N06AB05, N06AB06, N06AB07, N06AB08, N06AB09, N06AB10</p>
SNRIs	<p>N06AX16, N06AX17, N06AX21 N06AX23</p>
Lithium	N05AN01
Gold salts	<p>M01CB M01CB01 M01CB02 M01CB03 M01CB04</p>
Corticosteroids (oral) Glucocorticoids	<p>H02AB01 H02AB02 H02AB03 H02AB04 H02AB05 H02AB06 H02AB07 H02AB08 H02AB09 H02AB10</p>

<p>Mineralocorticoids</p> <p>CS combinations</p> <p>Corticosteroids (inhaled) Glucocorticoids (little evidence of risk)</p> <p>Injectable (dexamethasone, betamethasone)</p>	<p>H02AB11 H02AB12 H02AB13 H02AB14 H02AB15 H02AB17 H02AA01 H02AA02 H02AA03 H02BX01</p> <p>R03BA01 R03BA02 R03BA03 R03BA04 R03BA05 R03BA06 R03BA07 R03BA08 R03BA09</p> <p>S02BA06 S02BA07</p>
<p>Ergotamine And related compounds</p> <p>+ non-psycholeptics + psycholeptics</p>	<p>N02CA02 N02CA04 N02CA)7 N02CA52 N02CA72</p>
<p>Statins</p> <p>Plain</p> <p>Combinations +lipid modifying agent</p> <p>+other drug class</p>	<p>C10AA01 C10AA02 C10AA03 C10AA04 C10AA05 C10AA06 C10AA07 C10AA08</p> <p>C10BA01 C10BA02 C10BA03 C10BA04 C10BA05 C10BA06 C10BA07 C10BA08 C10BA09 C10BX01</p>

WP1 Table of exposures with known risks

	<p>C10BX02 C10BX03 C10BX04 C10BX05 C10BX06 C10BX07 C10BX08 C10BX09 C10BX10 C10BX11 C10BX12 C10BX13 C10BX14 C10BX15 C10BX16 C10BX17 C10BX18</p>
Tetracyclines	<p>J01AA01 J01AA02 J01AA03 J01AA04 J01AA05 J01AA06 J01AA07 J01AA08 J01AA09 J01AA10 J01AA11 J01AA12 J01AA13 J01AA14 J01AA15 J01AA20 J01AA56</p>
Colchicine	M04AC01
Misoprostol + NAPROXEN	<p>A02BB01 G02AD06 M01AE56</p>
Mifepristone Combinations	<p>G03XB01 G03XB51</p>
Ondansetron	A04AA01
Rifaximin	<p>A07AA11 D06AX11</p>
Sulfasalazine	A07EC01
Folate antagonists	<p>L01BA01 L01BA03, L01BA04, L01BA05</p>
Antipsychotics (from Creeley & Denton 2019), including Olanzapine	<p>N05AD01 N05AE04</p>

WP1 Table of exposures with known risks

Haloperidol	N05AE05
Risperidone	N05AH02
Quetiapine	N05AH03
Aripiprazole	N05AH04
Clozapine	N05AH05
Risperidone	N05AX08
Ziprasidone	N05AX12
Promethazine	
Pregabalin	N03AX16

Table 3 Conditions considered a risk for adverse outcomes – codes & references

Condition or characteristic	Code	Reference
Maternal age		https://www.webmd.com/baby/4-common-causes-miscarriage#1
Obesity	E66.x	Hsu et al 2021
Family history of congenital malformations Maternal CHD Affected siblings and twins	Z87.798	Liu S et al 2013 Brodwall et al 2017
Toxic effects of substances nonmedicinal	T51 toxic effect of alcohol T52 toxic effects of organic solvents T53 toxic effect of halogen derivates T54 Toxic effects of corrosive substances T56 Metals T57 Inorganic substance T58 Carbon monoxide T59 Other gases, fumes and vapors	
Heavy alcohol use	E5.x, F10.x, G62.1, I42.6, K29.2, K70.0, K70.3, K70.9, T51.x, Z50.2, Z71.4, Z72.1 O99.310 Alcohol use complicating pregnancy, unspecified trimester O99.311 Alcohol use complicating pregnancy, first trimester O99.312 Alcohol use complicating pregnancy, second trimester O99.313 Alcohol use complicating pregnancy, third trimester In cause-of-death statistics on alcohol related deaths following codes are included in the UK: E24.4, F10, G31.2, G62.1, G72.1, I42.6, K29.2, K70, K85.2, K86.0, Q86.0, R78.0, X45, X65, Y15. https://www.ons.gov.uk/peoplepopulationandcommunity/healthandsocialcare/causesofdeath/bulletins/alcoholrelateddeathsintheunitedkingdom/registeredin2019#measuring-the-data	Hsu et al 2021 https://icd.codes/icd10/cm/O9931

WP1 Table of exposures with known risks

	In Finland the list is as follows: F10, G31.2, G40.51, G62.1, G72.1, I42.6, K29.2, K70, K86.0, K85.2, O35.4, P04.3, Q86.0, X45 https://www.stat.fi/til/ksyyt/ksyyt_2018-11-12_luo_001_en.pdf	
Drug abuse / substance misuse	F11.x-F16.x, F18.x, F19.x, Z71.5, Z72.2 O99.3 - non-specific	Hsu et al 2021
Smoking	O99.33 pregnancy smoking F17.2 nicotine dependence Z72.0 tobacco use	https://www.codingstrategies.com/pdf/Nicotine%20Coding%20Job%20Aid%202016.pdf
Malnutrition	E40-E46	
Congenital CMV	P35.1	Barlinn et al 2018
Rubella	B06	
Toxoplasma	B58	
Febrile illness	R50.9 fever unspecified B50.9 Plasmodium falciparum A32.9 Listeria monocytogenes B17.2 Hepatitis E B00.82 herpes simplex virus disease, B54 malaria, A90 Dengue, A75.3 scrub typhus A01.00 typhoid fever severe. O86.04 Obstetric sepsis.	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK525177/ Graham 2020, Czeizel et al 2008 Yang et al 2021
Cancer	Any malignancy, including lymphoma and leukemia, except malignant neoplasm of skin C00.x-C26.x, C30.x-C34.x, C37.x-C41.x, C43.x, C45.x-C58.x, C60.x-C76.x, C81.x-C85.x, C88.x, C90.x-C97.x Metastatic cancer C77.x-C80.x We have excluded D codes, as these may be false positives for cancer diagnosis.	Hsu et al 2021
Autoimmune conditions	Addison's disease E27.1, E27.2 Ankylosing spondylitis M45, M08.1 Behcet's disease M35.2 Buerger's syndrome M31.1B, DI7.31 Celiac disease K90.0 Crohn's disease K50 Dermatitis herpetiformis L13.0 Diabetes mellitus type E10 Dupuytren's disease M72.0 Erythema nodosum L52 Goodpasture's syndrome M31.0 Graves' disease E05.0 Guillain-Barre syndrome G61.0 Haemolytic anaemia D59.0, D59.1 Hashimoto's thyroiditis E06.3 Henoch-Schönlein purpura D69.0 ITP D69.3 Kawasaki syndrome M30.3 Localized lupus erythematosus L93	Harpsøe et al 2014 Howley et al 2016 Williams et al 2019 Yalcin et al 2017

WP1 Table of exposures with known risks

	<p>Localized scleroderma L94.0, L94.1, L94.3 Myasthenia gravis G70.0 Multiple sclerosis G35 Pemphigoid L12 Pernicious anaemia D51.0 Pemphigus foliaceus L10.2 Pemphigus vulgaris L10.0 Polyarteritis nodosa M30.0 Polymyositis/dermatomyositis M33 Primary biliary cirrhosis K74.3 Psoriasis L40 Rheumatic fever I00, I01 Rheumatoid arthritis M05, M06 Raynaud’ s phenomenon DI73.0 Reiter’ s disease M02.3 Sarcoidosis D86 Sjogren’ s syndrome M35.0 Sympathetic ophthalmia H44.1B Systemic lupus erythematosus M32 Systemic scleroderma M34</p>	
SLE - CHD and all adverse outcomes	M32	Vinet et al 2015 Bundhun PK et al 2017,
Urinary tract infection (UTI) (Howley et al 2018) and / or associated exposure to antibacterials (Li et al 2020)	<p>Combination of diagnosis and symptoms has higher positive predictive value for UTI Cystitis N30 Acute Cystitis N30.0, N30.00, N30.01 Other Chronic Cystitis N30.2, N30.20, N30.21 Other Cystitis N30.8, N30.80, N30.81 Cystitis Unspecified N30.9, N30.90, N30.91 UTI (site not specified) N39.0 Acute Pyelonephritis N10 Nonobstructive Reflux-Associated Chronic Pyelonephritis N11.0 Chronic Obstructive Pyelonephritis N11.1 Pyonephritis N13.6</p> <p>UTI Related Symptoms Pain Associated with Micturition R30 Dysuria R30.0 Frequency of Micturition R35.0 Urgency of Urination R39.15</p>	<p>Germanos et al 2020 Cleves et al 008 Howley et al 2018 Li et al 2020</p>
Diabetes	E10.x-E14.x	Hsu et al 2021 Loffredo et al 2001
Severe hypertension	I10.x-I13.x, I15.x	Hsu et al 2021
Chronic renal disease	<p>CKD N18 CKD Stage 5 (eGFR <15) N185 CKD Stage 4 (eGFR 15-29) N184 CKD Stage 3 (eGFR 30-59) N183 CKD Stage 2 (eGFR 60-89) N182 CKD Stage 1 (eGFR ≥90) N181 Acute renal failure N17 Unspecified renal failure N19 Dependence on renal dialysis Z992</p>	Friberg et al 2018

WP1 Table of exposures with known risks

	Adjustment and management of vascular access device Z492 Creation of arterio-venous fistula from artery in the upper limb PBL (procedure codes) Repair surgery of arterio-venous fistula in the upper limb PBU (procedure codes) Haemodialysis, chronic DR016 Peritoneal dialysis, chronic DR024	
Anatomical anomalies (uterus or cervix)	Q51.9	
Polycystic ovaries	E28.2	
PKU	E70.0	https://lhncbc.nlm.nih.gov/newbornscreening/codes/nb/sc/condition/PKU.html
Chromosomal anomalies	Q90-Q99.9	

Table 4 ATCs for former class X medicines

Medication	Code
Valproate	N03AG01
Methotrexate	L01BA01 L04AX03
Ribavirin	J05AP01
Triazolam	N05CD05
Bosentan	C02KX01
Aliskiren	C09XA02 C09XA53C09XA52 C09XA54 C09DX02
Levonorgestrel	G03AC03 G03AD01 G03FA11 G03FB09 G03AA07 G03AB03
Ulipristal	G03AD02 G03XB02
Griseofulvin	D01AA08 D01BA01
Methylene blue	V03AB17 V04CG05
Oxytocin	G02AC01 H01BB02
Riociguat	C02KX05

Isotrenitoin	D10AD04 D10BA01 D10AD54
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Table 5. Medicines affecting breastfeeding
(not listed elsewhere)

Medicine or group	ATC code
Oestrogens	G03A (contraceptives, in combinations) G03C G03F (combinations) L02AA
Diuretics	C03 C07C (combinations) C02L (combinations) C07D (combinations) C08G (combinations) C09BA (combinations) C09DA (combinations)
Opioids	N01AH anaesthetics N02A oral and injectable N02AG (combinations) N02AJ (combinations) N02AX (includes tramadol) N07BC for opioid dependence
Oxytocin and derivatives, injected	H01BB02 H01BB03
Alcohol	No ATC code. Codes for heavy alcohol use are listed above.
Sympathomimetics, including amphetamines	N06BA R03C R03A (inhaled)
Anticholinergics (antimuscarinics)	R03BB A03AA (combinations not included) N04A
Promethazine teoclate (oral antihistamine and also used as an antipsychotic (as the hydrochloride))	R06AD02
Antidepressants, particularly SSRIs	N06AB02, N06AB03, N06AB04, N06AB05, N06AB06,

	N06AB07, N06AB08, N06AB09, N06AB10
Ergotamine And related compounds + non-psycholeptics + psycholeptics	N02CA02 N02CA04 N02CA)7 N02CA52 N02CA72
Antipsychotics (from Creeley & Denton 2019), including Olanzapine Haloperidol Risperidone Quetiapine Aripiprazole Clozapine Risperidone Ziprasidone Promethazine Breastfeeding is not advised for clozapine, olanzapine and other antipsychotics	N05AD01 N05AE04 N05AE05 N05AH02 N05AH03 N05AH04 N05AH05 N05AX08 N05AX12
Corticosteroids, injected	S02BA06 S02BA07

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Exemplar Text from Jordan et al 2016

To minimise **confounding by co-exposure**, we achieved a relatively homogeneous population by excluding infants: 1) with EUROCAT coding[37] indicating known teratogenic syndromes (EUROCAT subgroups a182-84, a186) 2) exposed to medicines more closely associated with congenital anomalies than SSRIs during the

91 days either side of 1st day of LMP: anti-epileptic drugs (AEDs) (N03)[61]; coumarins (B01AA), mainly warfarin[62]; insulins (A10A)[63].

We examined, but did not exclude, SSRI exposed cases for: 1) exposure to other potentially teratogenic prescription medicines 91 days either side of 1st day of LMP: systemic isotretinoin (D10BA); angiotensin converting enzyme inhibitors or angiotensin II blockers (C09); lithium (N05AN); benzodiazepines (N05BA); first generation antipsychotics (N05AA through N05AG); second generation antipsychotics (N05AH, N05AL, N05AX); carbimazole (H03BB); thyroxine (N03AA); medicines rarely prescribed in primary care but associated with anomalies: aminoglycosides, ergot derivatives, lindane, gold salts, penicillamine, methotrexate, chloroquine, radiopharmaceuticals[64]; 2) heavy alcohol use and substance misuse (Wales only); 3) maternal conditions indicating that the woman might not be considered to be from the normal healthy population: hospital admission for cancer; thyroid disorders; phenylketonuria; maternal congenital anomalies[65]; 4) maternal siblings with anomalies.

- AEDs,
- coumarins
- Anti-thyroid (methimazole not in UK)
- Diabetes is a risk factor for many outcomes.
- Heavy alcohol, substance misuse
- angiotensin converting enzyme inhibitors or angiotensin II blockers (C09);
- lithium (N05AN);
- benzodiazepines (N05BA);
- first generation antipsychotics (N05AA through N05AG);
- second generation antipsychotics (N05AH, N05AL, N05AX);
- carbimazole (H03BB); thyroxine (N03AA);
- medicines rarely prescribed in primary care but associated with anomalies: aminoglycosides, ergot derivatives, lindane, gold salts, penicillamine, methotrexate, retinoids (oral only), chloroquine, radiopharmaceuticals[64]; (Manual review of standard text)
- maternal conditions indicating that the woman might not be considered to be from the normal healthy population: hospital admission for cancer; thyroid disorders; SLE; phenylketonuria; maternal congenital anomalies[65];
- maternal siblings with anomalies (likely only for anomalies, and only within database timeframe).